

THE ROLE OF AMIR TEMUR'S MILITARY STRATEGY IN THE MILITARY-PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract.

The culture created during the time of these two states: Kushanov and Kushanids (before Islam) and Temurids (after Islam), attracted the attention of the whole world, is the pride of our Uzbek people, all the peoples of Central Asia. The founder of the Temurid state, Amir Temur, is a great man who has left an inexhaustible mark on history. His services in the field of public administration, military, political, social, cultural, religious spheres are unprecedented.

Key words.

great commander, military art, military talents, soldiers, battlefield, Temur army, heroism.

Amir Temur is a great man who left an indelible mark on history: a creator, a great statesman, a skilled commander, a patron of science and culture. Timur's state was a centralized state compared to his time. According to the idea of the founder of this state, Amir Temur, the goals and interests of all social strata of the country - sayyids and priests, scientists and virtuous people, artisans, farmers, sipahis, merchants and others - should be strictly protected by the councils and the Council had to govern. Amir Temur ruled the country for 35 years. He spent many military campaigns and battles [2]. Conquered many countries. The military talent of Amir Temur played a big role in the conquest of these countries. His military talent manifested itself mainly in two directions - as a skillful military organizer and as a well-known commander.

The upbringing of every citizen living in the territory of Uzbekistan, representatives of all nations and peoples and their children as a perfect person is one of the highest goals of our independent republic. In this regard, the role of our great-grandfathers in the past is incomparable. It is known that the work "Temur Tuzuklari", written by Sahibkiron Amir Temur and his life path in studying the history of our great-grandfather, guarantees that he will be able to use his knowledge and skills in the field of educating youth in real life.

As a great commander and innovator, military organizer, Amir Temur managed to create a highly disciplined army, skillfully manage army units during the battle, skillfully direct military forces to places where the fate of the battle will be decided, and everyone is able to overcome obstacles and traps with enterprise, maintain morale in the army at the required level. Sahibkiron carefully studies and analyzes the structure of the Turkic-Mongolian peoples, especially the army of Genghis Khan, their fighting techniques and makes the necessary changes. Although the structure of the army created by Amir Temur was somewhat close to the system and structure of the army created by Genghis Khan, it differed in the following important aspects:

1. The army of Amir Temur did not have a national character, while the army of Genghis Khan consisted of the people's army, which was sent to military service on the basis of total dedication.

2. During the time of Genghis Khan, the nomadic masses formed the basis of the army. The army of Amir Temur received a significant number of soldiers from the settled population, engaged in agriculture, crafts, as well as cattle breeders, at the special request of the commander in chief.

3. There were many infantry units in the army of Amir Temur, as well as horsemen, who formed the basis of the armed forces. It is known that the army of Genghis Khan did not have foot soldiers, with the exception of the recruit population of the conquered countries.

4. Amir Temur was one of the first in the East to introduce firearms into his army, i.e. guns.

5. Sahibgiron organized special military units from the infantry, which are fighting in the highlands.

6. Amir Temur was the first in the history of world military art to introduce the procedure for deploying seven types of troops on the battlefield.

7. In the army of Amir Temur there were detachments made up of women who stood in the same line with men during the battle and showed examples of heroism and stamina.

According to historical sources, cavalymen were considered the most combat-ready part of Amir Temur's army, they were divided into cavalry groups armed with heavy and light weapons. The cavalry, lightly armed with bows, longbows and swords, was mainly engaged in reconnaissance and guarding, and had the right to fight enemy forces only when absolutely necessary. The heavily armored cavalry, armed with helmets, armour, swords, bows, shields and spears, consisted of sar warriors, withstood the main attack of the enemy's and played a major role in deciding the outcome of the battle. .

Before leaving for the campaign, Amir Temur called the state, ministers, generals, beks and amirs to a military council. At the same time, a special order was announced - tungala - for the collection of troops from various regions and regions of the country, as well as from subordinate countries. The order was quickly delivered to the right places by a high-ranking adjutant-tawachi of the commander-in-chief. In addition to collecting soldiers, Tawachi was also responsible for controlling the location of army units in a camp or on a campaign, order of battle and movement from one place to another.

According to the writings of Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, Amir Temur Dashti, before the campaign against Kypchak (1390-1391), planned to provide the army with an annual supply of food, weapons, clothing and other items necessary for the campaign. deputies. Each cavalryman was assigned one bow, 30 arrows, one bow, one shield, and one additional horse. During the campaign, an additional horse was allocated for every ten warriors. During the campaign, every ten soldiers received one tent, two shovels, one pitchfork, one scythe, one saw, one ax and 100 pieces of spears.

According to Tuzuklari Temur, for every ten sakkits of ordinary soldiers, one tent was given during the journey. Each warrior had two horses, a bow, a sword, a sword, a sword, a bag, ten spears, a saw and a leather bag (chanakh). All five of Sarah's warriors are housed in the same tent. Each of them was provided with a helmet, armor, sword, arrows, bow and arrows, as well as the number of horses specified in the order.

The Ten had a separate tent. He was armed with a spear, sword, bow and arrow and was entitled to five additional horses. Yuzbegi also had a separate tent. His weapons consisted of sword, bow and arrow, sword, bow, mace and axe. He

was given ten additional names. In addition to the Mingbegi tent, an umbrella is also provided. He is armed with various types of weapons such as helmet, armor (chakhoroina), savut, spear, sword, bow and arrows.

, four well-known military leaders were appointed to the post of commander of the first rank, i.e. backarbegi. One of the emirs of Dongdar was given the post of amirul-umaro and he performed the functions of the supreme commander in chief, that is, the deputy of Amir Temur. Amirul-umaro commanded the army in wars and battles in which Sahibkiran did not directly participate. In addition to those mentioned, twelve more guardsmen were involved in the command of the army. A cavalry of a thousand people was commanded by the first bek, a group of two thousand horsemen - by the second bek, a group of three thousand horsemen - by the third bek, an army of twelve thousand horsemen - by the twelfth bek.

The lower-level commander was subordinate to a general who held a higher position than he. Timur's army consisted of armies formed on the basis of ten military formations. The army was divided into "district" - 10 thousand, "Khazars" - thousandths, "hoshin-hundreds" and "aiyls" - ten thousandths. The number of soldiers in the districts was 10,000 people, and the army - over 100,000 people. Amir Temur established such military positions as "head of the district" to command ten thousand troops, "mirihazar" for thousands of detachments, "hoshunboshi" for hundreds and "aiboshi" for dozens. [1].

Amir Temur selects people who have shown their skills on the battlefield, rather than appointing them through acquaintances. Sahibgiron says about this: "I ordered that when ten people come together who have worked hard from the original warriors and seasoned in battles, which of them had the greatest courage and courage, the consent and approval of the remaining nine. since he enslaves them, let them choose him as their leader and call his horse the head of ten. If there are only ten chiefs, let them appoint one of them who has worked harder, gained experience on the battlefields and became famous in the army, and they will call him a centurion. If ten centurions gather, then they must choose from the princes one smart, courageous and valuable amir, and let him be called a thousand-bashi and be glorified by a thousand-bashi amir[3].

Amir Temur appointed his sons and grandsons as chief commanders of the Sipokhs. He was succeeded by his eldest son Muhammad Jahangir. He was awarded the Balkh region and 12 thousand horsemen. He ordered his second son, Umarshaikh, to receive a reward for the province of Persia and ten thousand horsemen. The third son - Mironshah was given the right to receive awards for the

regions of Azerbaijan, Iraq, Armenia and 9,000 cavalrymen. The fourth son, Shahrukh, had the right to receive as a reward the regions of Khorasan, Jurjan, Mazendaran, Seyistan and seven thousand horsemen. And to his grandchildren, depending on their abilities, he gives the right to receive awards from one province to three thousand to seven thousand cavalry.

Amir Temur regulates both legal and moral aspects of the protection of soldiers, their salaries, the attitude of navkars to their beks, and beks to their navkars. Demands that Navkars be correct and fair. All three hundred and thirteen emirs were smart and skillful commanders. Only the one who knew the secrets of battle, who could lead armies into battle without losing his temper in the midst of war, who could lead armies into battle, who could quickly correct the deficiency in the ranks of the army, was considered worthy of a leader and ruler.

Those who excelled in swordsmanship were appointed ten chiefs for the first time, centurions for the second time, and thousandth chiefs for the third time. The service of any soldier was not left without attention, because they were in the public service and did not spare their eternal life for the sake of the mortal world, and it was believed that they deserved to be rewarded and provided with material support.

Those who respect elders and receive useful advice from them. He called them the pillars of the kingdom's enterprise. The Navkar, who was captured by Ganim, was not killed, he was given complete freedom of action. If he accepts the service, he is a slave, if he does not agree, he will be released. If a servant was appointed ruler of a country, he was sentenced to death if he made an agreement with the enemy through treachery and surrendered property to him.

The servant who defended the country and did not allow the enemy to leave was elevated to a high rank. Any warrior who forgets about salary and loyalty and during the service turns away from his master and comes to Amir Temur, he considered such a person his worst enemy. Before the battle, he carefully studied the country to which he was going to go. If it were possible to solve the problem peacefully, it would be wrong to use weapons there. Amir Temur declared war on any country where tyranny, violence, oppression and injustice were strong, and the people were dissatisfied with their king. Amir Temur was a great commander and statesman. He sincerely served his community with great military genius and determination. The heritage of military art created by him has taken a worthy place in the heritage of world military art and is now being enriched with new content.

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